

ESDC course on Strategic Communication in the Context of Security and Defence, Bucharest 14 - 18 September 2020

PROGRAMME

**Strategic Communication in the Context of Security and Defence Course
Bucharest, 14–18.09.2020**

Time/ Date	Monday, 14 September	Tuesday, 15 September	Wednesday, 16 September	Thursday, 17 September	Friday, 18 September
09.00- 10.30	Registration	<p>Panel 4: EU Strategic Environment and Decision-Making</p> <p>Mihaela Ștefan Ministry of Foreign Affairs</p> <p>Mădălina Mocanu Communication Officer European Commission DG Migration and Home Affairs <i>(on-line intervention),</i></p> <p>Representative European External Action Service (TBC) <i>(on-line intervention),</i></p>	<p>Panel 8: Strategy and Crisis Management and Crisis Communications in the Digital Ecosystem</p> <p>Raed Arafat, Secretary of State, Ministry of Internal Affairs</p> <p><i>Facilitator: Dr Bogdan Marinescu, CNAI</i></p>	<p>Panel 10: The Digital Ecosystem for StratCom/ Mitigating Communication Crisis Process, planning and implementation</p> <p>Radu Magdin, Smartlink Communications</p> <p>Aitana Radu, University of Malta, Department of Information Policy and Governance <i>(on-line intervention)</i></p> <p>Cristina Ivan, Researcher, Faculty for Intelligence Studies, “Mihai Viteazul” National Intelligence Academy</p>	<p>RECAP Panel</p> <p>Syndicates <i>Presentation of team assignments</i></p> <p>Facilitator: Flavia Durach, National University of Political Studies and Public Administration</p>

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		<p><i>Moderator: Kieran Doyle, National University of Ireland, Maynooth (on-line intervention),</i></p>		<p><i>(on-line intervention)</i></p> <p>Irena Chiru, Dean, Faculty for Intelligence Studies, “Mihai Viteazul” National Intelligence Academy <i>(on-line intervention)</i></p> <p>Corina Buzoianu, National University of Political Studies and Public Administration</p> <p><i>Moderator: Bianca Cheregi, National University of Political Studies and Public Administration</i></p>	
10.30-11.00	<p>Opening Speeches</p> <p>Dirk Dubois <i>(on-line intervention),</i> Head of European Security and Defence College</p> <p>Amb. Sorin Ducaru <i>(on-line intervention),</i> Director of EU SATCEN Special Advisor to the Global Commission on Cyberstability</p> <p>Andrei Țărnea Director of the Communication and Public</p>	Coffee Break	Coffee Break	Coffee Break	Coffee Break

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	<p>Diplomacy Department, Ministry of Foreign Affairs</p> <p>Catalin Andrus Rector of Alexandru Ioan Cuza Police Academy</p> <p><i>Moderator: Prof Alina Bârgăoanu, professor and dean, College of Communication and Public Relations & course director</i></p> <p><i>Adrian Lazaroaia European Security and Defence College Training Manager</i></p>				
11.00-12.30	<p>11.00-11.15 Eastern Partnership (EaP) Dr. Simion Costea <i>(on-line intervention)</i></p> <p>11.15-12:30 Panel 1: The EU Global Strategy and Its Implementation Dirk Dubois, Head of European Security and Defence College <i>(on-line intervention)</i></p>	<p>Panel 5: StratCom Fundamentals (Persuasion, campaign planning and implementation. Conflict analysis and dialogue)</p> <p>Maria Cernat, National University of Political Studies and Public Administration</p> <p>Irena Chiru "Mihai Viteazul" National Intelligence Academy</p>	<p>Panel 9: Communicating the EU: CSDP Missions and Operations</p> <p>Kieran Doyle, National University of Ireland, Maynooth <i>(on-line intervention)</i></p> <p>Mikko Harjulehto Policy and Strategic Communication Officer</p>	<p>Panel 11: StratCom - Case Studies Mitigating Communication Crises. Crisis Communication Simulation</p> <p>Corina Buzoianu, National University of Political Studies and Public Administration</p>	<p>Closing ceremony</p> <p>Catalin Andrus Police Academy Alexandru Ioan Cuza, Rector</p> <p>Prof Alina Bârgăoanu, professor and dean, College of Communication and Public Relations & course director</p> <p>Adrian Lazaroaia</p>

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	<p>Mircea Mîndrescu New Strategy Center, CNAI, ESDC EAB Chair</p> <p>Andrei Țârnea Director of the Communication and Public Diplomacy Department, Ministry of Foreign Affairs</p> <p><i>Moderator: Prof Alina Bârgăoanu, professor and dean, College of Communication and Public Relations & course director</i></p>	<p><i>(on-line intervention),</i></p> <p>Cristina Ivan, Researcher, Faculty for Intelligence Studies, “Mihai Viteazul” National Intelligence Academy <i>(on-line intervention)</i></p> <p>Kieran Doyle, National University of Ireland, Maynooth <i>(on-line intervention),</i></p> <p><i>Moderator: Moderator: Dr Bogdan Marinescu, CNAI</i></p>	<p>European External Action Service <i>(on-line intervention)</i></p> <p>Ioana Lachana EULEX Kosovo Head of Press Office/Spokesperson <i>(on-line intervention)</i></p> <p>Ferdinand Koenig Eupol Cops <i>(on-line intervention)</i></p> <p>Anna Palmen EUAM Irak Press & Public Information Officer <i>(on-line intervention)</i></p> <p><i>Moderator: Bogdan Marinescu</i></p>		<p>European Security and Defence College</p> <p>Lucia Sava, Ministry of Foreign Affairs</p> <p>Certificates Adrian Lazaroaia European Security and Defence College</p> <p>Viorel Veliscu CNAI, Director</p> <p>Prof Alina Bârgăoanu, professor and dean, College of Communication and Public Relations & course director</p>
12.30-13.30	LUNCH BREAK Marriott	LUNCH BREAK Marriott	LUNCH BREAK Marriott	LUNCH BREAK Marriott	LUNCH BREAK Marriott
13.30-15.00	Panel 2: StratCom – EU vs. NATO Approach	Panel 6: StratCom Concepts (Communication effects, narrative analysis and development, the role of mass media in the implementation of StratCom priorities)	Individual work - team assignments	Panel 12: Disinformation, Fake News, Propaganda	Departure of participants
	Mircea Mîndrescu New Strategy Center, CNAI, ESDC EAB Chair		<i>(details on organisation during Panel 2 on Monday 14.09.2020)</i>	Alina Bârgăoanu, professor and dean, College of Communication and Public Relations & course director	

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	<p>National University of Political Studies and Public Administration (TBC)</p> <p><i>Moderator:</i> Moderator: Dr Bogdan Marinescu, CNAI</p>	<p>Dan Sultănescu <i>(on-line intervention)</i> National University of Political Studies and Public Administration</p> <p>Constantin Spînu, Ministry of National Defence</p> <p>Constantin Bălan, Ministry of National Defence <i>Moderator: Bogdan Marinescu</i></p>		<p>Antonio Momoc, Dean, FJSC, University of Bucharest</p> <p>Dan Dungaciu, University of Bucharest, Romanian Academy</p> <p>Miglinaite Raimonda European External Action Service <i>(on-line intervention)</i></p> <p><i>Moderator: Bianca Cheregi, National University of Political Studies and Public Administration</i></p>	
15:00-15:30	Coffee Break	Coffee Break		Coffee Break	

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<p>15.30-17.00</p>	<p>Panel 3: Leadership and Decision-Making</p> <p><i>Simulation Exercises Team dynamics Intro to team assignments</i></p> <p>Facilitator: Flavia Durach, National University of Political Studies and Public Administration</p>	<p>Panel 7 – Communicating EU at Home and Abroad</p> <p>Lucia Sava, Ministry of Foreign Affairs Adviser to the Minister</p> <p>Dan Cărbunaru, National University of Political Studies and Public Administration/Calea Europeană</p> <p>Representative, European External Action Service (TBC)</p> <p><i>Moderator: Robert Lupitu, Editor in Chief, Calea Europeana</i></p>		<p>Panel 13: The Role of StratCom in Dealing with Cybersecurity, and Hybrid Threats</p> <p>Dragoş Preda, State Secretary for Telecommunications at Ministry of Transport, Infrastructure and Communication</p> <p>Andrei Borzeanu, CERT-RO</p> <p>Daniel Ioniţă, Cybersecurity Manager CYMED/INFOWORLD</p> <p><i>Moderator: Dr Bogdan Marinescu, CNAI</i></p>	
<p>18.00-21.00</p>	<p>Welcome cocktail <i>Hosted by CNAI at Hotel Marriott</i></p>			<p>Official Dinner Hosted by CNAI</p>	